

The strategic importance of intellectual capital to airline financial success

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>RESEARCH ARTICLE</p> <p>Keywords: Aviation Industry Intellectual Capital Human Capital Customer Capital Structural Capital</p> <p>Received: 25 November 2024 Revised: 16 December 2024 Accepted: 24 December 2024</p>	<p>The objective of this study is to examine the relationship between the various elements that constitute intellectual capital and the financial profitability of airline companies. The study included data from 12 airline companies in Star Alliance for the period between 2005 and 2023. The profitability ratios of the airline companies were employed as the dependent variable, while the three elements of intellectual capital, namely human capital, structural capital and customer capital, were utilised as independent variables. Firstly, ratios of intellectual capital and profitability were calculated for all airline companies. A specific pre-test analysis was conducted on the data. The Dumitrescu and Hurlin panel causality analysis method was employed to investigate the influence of the variables in question. It can thus be concluded that there is a positive and unidirectional causal relationship between customer capital and return on assets and equity, and a positive and bidirectional causal relationship between human capital and return on assets and equity. Furthermore, the analysis revealed that there is no causality from return on assets and equity to customer capital.</p>

1. Introduction

In recent times, the production, distribution and utilization of knowledge have entered an era characterized by the knowledge economy. This new economic paradigm has been shaped by a high added value and innovative approach to technology, production and production. The input of the knowledge economy is contingent upon the acquisition of information. Those who are able to obtain this information correctly will gain a competitive advantage in the market. The growth of firms may be achieved through the enhancement of productivity, the development of a distinctive brand identity, the implementation of effective strategic management, and the optimal utilization of human capital. It is relatively straightforward to record and utilize physical capital. However, knowledge capital is challenging to monitor and quantify (Akın, 2019, p. 10). At this juncture, we encounter the concept of intellectual capital.

The concept of intellectual capital was first articulated by John Kenneth Galbraith, a US economist, in 1969. In the view of the economist, intellectual capital is not merely the output of human intelligence; it is also the aggregate of intellectual activities. The concept of intellectual capital was first introduced into the literature in 1975 by Michael Kalecki in an article that referenced John. In his article, Michael Kalecki highlighted the issue by questioning whether the acquisition of intellectual capital over the intervening period had been noticed. The article published by the researcher Thomas Stewart in 1991 is considered to be a landmark text

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in the field of intellectual capital, as it deals with the concept in its current meaning. Despite extensive research on intellectual capital in the literature, it gained prominence in the 1990s (Uyaroğlu, 2019, pp. 4–5).

In essence, intellectual capital represents the collective sum of intangible assets, including intellectual property rights, patents, privileges, and reputation, that contribute to an organization's capacity to execute its operations effectively. In other words, intellectual capital is the capacity to transform knowledge into economic value. In the view of Thomas Stewart, intellectual capital represents the utilization of intellectual material for the generation of profit. In other words, he defines it as comprising knowledge, experience and intellectual property. The future success of a firm is contingent upon the manner in which its intellectual capital is managed. It constitutes a set of assets that cannot be obtained directly from the company statements (Genç, 2018, pp. 25–26).

Intellectual capital represents the most fundamental instrument for navigating the uncertainty, information needs and change that arise as a consequence of globalization and the intensification of competition. In the contemporary business environment, the ability to gain a competitive advantage is closely linked to the value and management of intellectual capital, rather than the characteristics of the material resources that firms possess. The continuity of a firm in the business environment is contingent upon the effective management of its intellectual capital, which is defined as the aggregate value created by employees, management strategy, internal processes, systems and relationships with customers. It is therefore crucial to analyse, measure, utilize and effectively manage intellectual capital (Şanal & Ölçer, 2007, p. 479–480).

The aviation industry has become one of the most fundamental sectors of the international economy as a consequence of globalization and technological developments (Yaşar & Kiracı, 2017). It is therefore evident that the sustainable financial success of airline companies is contingent upon the effective utilization of both physical and financial data, coupled with the ascription of due value and importance to the elements that affect performance, such as intellectual capital. The elements of intellectual capital, including human capital, structural capital and customer capital, play an active role in conferring a competitive advantage on firms. This study analyses the influence of the intellectual capital of a significant airline alliance, such as Star Alliance, on financial profitability. The rationale for including Star Alliance members in the analysis is as follows: There are a number of key reasons for the inclusion of Star Alliance members in the analysis. The inclusion of Star Alliance members in the analysis is justified by the fact that they represent airline companies operating on a global scale, addressing a diverse customer base and fulfilling a range of operational processes. The aim of analyzing the intellectual capital of these airline companies is to achieve global competition, sustainable success and strategic superiority. A review of existing literature reveals a paucity of studies on the aviation sector. Accordingly, this study examines the impact of intellectual capital on financial performance in the aviation sector in great detail.

This study addresses the elements of intellectual capital and the significance of intellectual capital in the context of aviation. Subsequently, the study presents information regarding the significance, constraints, and analytical approach employed in the investigation. The study is concluded with the data obtained as a result of the analysis and the conclusion section.

1.1. Elements of Intellectual Capital

The constituent elements of intellectual capital are subject to analysis from a multiplicity of perspectives, including those of relationship capital, social capital, human capital, community capital, structural capital, deal capital, customer capital, and used capital. The discrepancy in classification stems from the disparate approaches and perspectives of the individuals responsible for defining these concepts, such as in the case of intellectual capital. The concept of intellectual capital can be broken down into three fundamental components. The relative importance of these components is contingent upon the structural characteristics of the firm in question. For instance, in the case of prominent software companies such as Microsoft, Yahoo and Google, the pivotal element is human capital. The value lies in the skills, knowledge and experience those individuals possess. In contrast, for McDonald's, structural capital is of greater consequence. Obtaining suitable products and delivering them to customers in a timely and complete manner is contingent upon the structure of the organization. This research will discuss three commonly used components of intellectual capital (Çalışkan, 2015, p. 123).

The term 'human capital' is used to describe the knowledge, experience, loyalty, teamwork, intelligence, problem-solving attitudes, entrepreneurship and leadership skills of the personnel employed by a firm. In recent periods of working life, investments in human capital are no longer regarded as a cost. Conversely, initiatives are undertaken with the objective of enhancing and developing the existing situation. Both internal and external investments have played an active role in intensifying competition. In other words, if a firm incorporates the knowledge and experience of its employees and manages them effectively, it will gain a competitive advantage over its rivals. Nevertheless, it is incumbent upon the company to enhance the sense of belonging among its employees by ensuring that they are duly valued and supported. Otherwise, the investment of time and resources in employees will be futile (Toraman, 2009, p. 99-100).

Structural capital represents the complement and support structure for the firm's human capital. Structural capital encompasses all information utilized within this domain, including the organization's hardware, database, brand, patents, software activity plans, systems, and processes. It is imperative that structural data be stored securely and made readily accessible when required. The principal objective is to circumvent operational issues in the event of personnel departures (Öztürk & Demirgüneş, 2008, p. 402). Structural capital encompasses the management information utilized by the firm during the production of its products or services, as well as the organizational culture and strategic plans. Structural capital serves as the framework within which the firm's resources are organized. It liberates knowledge from its reliance on human capital, while simultaneously providing support and structure to human capital (Demir & Demirel, 2011, p. 89).

Customer capital is not merely an indicator of the target audience for the firm; it is a multifaceted construct that encompasses a range of factors. In addition to the customer, the concept of customer capital also encompasses the company's suppliers, competitors and all other environmental factors. Customer capital comprises all external and internal processes that facilitate the acquisition and retention of customers, thereby ensuring the delivery of quality, reliable and continuous services. Furthermore, customer capital encompasses suppliers, which represent a crucial element in the commercial activities of firms, as well as the values that facilitate the firm's engagement with the market. Consequently, customer capital is also referred to as relational capital. The determination of customer and supplier capital is contingent upon the evaluation of pertinent information, banking data, and pertinent documents. It is imperative that customer and supplier relationships are not established with a transient and ephemeral perspective. It is essential that work is conducted in a manner that fosters mutual development and adds value to both parties, with a focus on long-term outcomes. Consequently, customer capital represents merely one potential avenue for firms to achieve success in the domain of intellectual capital. These three elements of intellectual capital are mutually reinforcing and exhibit a strong interrelationship (Toraman, 2009, pp. 100–101). Hsu and Fang (2008) reached the conclusion in their research that human capital has a positive effect on the other two elements.

1.2. Intellectual Capital in the Aviation Sector

One of the most significant and dynamic aspects of globalization is the aviation sector. As a consequence of technological advancement and the processes of globalization that have occurred over time, the levels of competition and dynamism have increased. Concurrently with these developments, the aviation sector has undergone significant changes and undergone a process of development. According to data from the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO), the number of flights performed annually has increased exponentially. In 1950, there were 100 million flights. By 1976, this figure had reached one billion, and by 2010, it had reached 5.216 billion. These developments in the aviation sector have a direct impact on both national and regional economies. In other words, there is a positive correlation between a country's income and its preference for airline transportation (Yüksel, 2014, pp. 8-9). In addition to the primary production criteria of labour, capital, resources and entrepreneurship, the information economy, which was a notable phenomenon in the 1990s, introduced a novel approach to enterprise management and an enhanced understanding of competition. This new approach has given rise to the concept of intellectual capital. Intellectual capital is the term used to describe all of the information and intangible assets that shape future value and are not reflected in the financial statements produced by general accounting in order to gain a competitive advantage. In the aviation sector, where growth and technological development are particularly rapid, the effective identification, valuation and management of intellectual capital – a key component of the

criterion of wealth – enables companies to participate in the competitive process on an ongoing basis, thereby ensuring sustainable competition. It is therefore essential to assess and quantify the various elements of intellectual capital collectively (Odabaşoğlu, 2019, p. 2). Given the recent proliferation of research and discourse surrounding intellectual capital, this study addresses the question of how such capital can be measured in the context of the aviation sector.

Figure 1. Human capital

Figure 2. Structural capital

Figure 3. Customer capital

The graphical representation of the three main elements of intellectual capital included in the analysis, namely human capital, customer capital and structural capital, are presented in Figures 1, 2 and 3. Upon examination of Figure 1, it becomes evident that human capital maintains a consistent trajectory throughout the duration of the analysis, with fluctuations occurring in select periods. It is hypothesized that investments or growth in human capital may have an impact on this factor. Figure 2 depicts a sudden and pronounced shift in structural capital over the specified period. In particular, it is observed that it becomes stationary after a period of rapid increase. It can be posited that the internal growth and technological investments experienced by airline firms had a significant impact at the outset. Figure 3 illustrates that the figure in question is particularly elevated during the initial periods. It is evident that the customer capital of airline companies undergoes significant fluctuations at the outset, but subsequently becomes relatively static.

2. Literature

The concept of intellectual capital has emerged as a pivotal area of focus for firms seeking to enhance their performance in the contemporary business landscape. Intellectual capital is a critical factor in gaining a competitive advantage and achieving sustainable growth. A review of the literature reveals a multitude of studies that examine the impact of the constituent elements of the concept of intellectual capital, particularly human, structural and customer capital, on financial performance across a range of sectors. The significance of intellectual capital in the aviation industry has increased in light of the intense competition and the knowledge-based operational structure that characterizes the sector. This section presents a review of studies examining the impact of intellectual capital on firm performance.

Genç et al. (2009), examined the relationship between human capital, exports and growth in the Turkish economy for the period 1980-2007. The authors employed Toda–Yamamoto causality tests as a means of analysis. The findings indicated that there is a unidirectional causality relationship from exports to human capital. Furthermore, it was observed that the Turkish economy requires a greater supply of human capital.

Karçioğlu and Özer (2014), was to ascertain the factors influencing the stock profits of 113 firms within the BIST manufacturing sector over the period 2002-2011. In their analysis, the researchers employed a panel data analysis method, utilizing exchange rate, oil prices and intellectual value-added coefficient data. As a consequence, no evidence was found to suggest a relationship between the variables.

Aksu (2016), conducted an analysis of the relationship between human capital and economic growth in Türkiye between the years 1960 and 2009. In his analysis, he examined the multivariate short- and long-run causality relationship between economic growth and a number of other variables, including education, health, employment, productivity, university enrollment, population growth, and survival time. The Granger test and the Toda-Yamamoto causality test were employed in the analysis. The findings indicated that there is no causality between human capital and economic growth.

Erdoğan and Dönmez (2014), investigated the correlation between intellectual capital data and the productivity of seven enterprises engaged in metal and machinery manufacturing between 2008 and 2011. In order to analyze the data, a panel unit root test was employed. In employing asset earning power and asset turnover rate as dependent variables, the sub-headings of intellectual capital were used as independent variables. Consequently, he concluded that there is a positive relationship between structural and human capital and the efficiency of the enterprise.

Odabaşoğlu (2018), examined the relationship between intellectual capital and financial ratios of 23 airline companies for the years 2007-2014. The panel unit root test was employed in the analysis. Consequently, the author concluded that there is a positive relationship between financial indicators and intellectual capital.

Buyuran and Şit (2021), conducted the effects of intellectual capital on the financial performance of 11 enterprises operating in the communication and transportation sector in BIST (Borsa Istanbul) between 2005 and 2020 were examined. In his analysis, he employed the AMG, CCE Mean Group estimators and Panel Regression methods. In his analysis, the independent variables were asset turnover, value added and the three dimensions of intellectual capital. The dependent variables were equity and return on assets. The findings indicated that intellectual capital exerts an influence on the financial performance of enterprises.

He and Luo (2022), investigated the relationship between intellectual capital and financial ratios of enterprises operating in China's general aviation sector between 2016 and 2020. In their analysis, the researchers employed a panel unit root test. The findings indicated that there is a negative relationship between human capital and solvency, while structural capital has no significant impact on financial ratios. Conversely, customer capital was identified as the primary driver of financial ratios.

Sakur and Güngör (2023), examined the effect of intellectual capital on the financial status of 102 enterprises operating in the industrial sector between 2008 and 2015 using panel data analysis. The study's findings indicate that intellectual capital exerts a positive influence on the financial performance of enterprises. Furthermore, he concluded that while enterprises attach significance to human capital, they neglect structural capital.

Sayed and Nefzi (2024), investigated the correlation between intellectual capital and the sustainable performance of ten major banks in Saudi Arabia. The analysis encompassed the data pertaining to the banks for the period between 2012 and 2022. The dependent variables were return on equity and net profit margin, while the independent variables were the number of intellectual capital multiples and its three elements. The analysis employed the ADF, PP unit root tests, descriptive statistics, correlation, and Panel Least Squares Estimation Results. The findings revealed that intellectual capital has a significant positive impact on the sustainable performance of banks in Saudi Arabia, with human capital efficiency exerting a particularly pronounced influence on return on equity and net profit margin.

Arı et al. (2024), examined the relationship between firm performance and corporate social responsibility in emerging markets, with a particular focus on the role of intellectual capital in mediating this interaction. A total of 380 companies from 24 emerging markets were included in the study between 2015 and 2021. A three-dimensional nested fixed-effect panel regression model was employed. The researchers observed an inverse relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance, as well as a significant relationship between intellectual capital and financial performance.

This literature review encompasses studies that investigate the influence of intellectual capital on financial performance across a range of industries and countries. The majority of studies indicate that intellectual capital has a considerable impact on the productivity and profitability of businesses. However, it is notable that there are discrepancies between the findings of each study. These discrepancies can be attributed to sector-specific attributes, the analytical techniques employed, and the variability in the scope of the research. Moreover, the paucity of studies concentrating on the aviation sector underscores the necessity for further investigation in this domain. Further research examining the nexus between airlines and intellectual capital will enhance our comprehension of these dynamics within the sectoral context.

3. Hypothesis

In light of the findings of the literature review and the objective of investigating the impact of intellectual capital elements on the profitability of Star Alliance member airlines, the following hypotheses are proposed.

- Hypothesis 1 (H1): A causal relationship exists between human capital efficiency and airlines' return on assets (ROA).

- Hypothesis 2 (H2): A causal relationship exists between customer capital efficiency and airlines' return on assets (ROA).

- Hypothesis 3 (H3): A causal relationship exists between structural capital efficiency and airlines' return on assets (ROA).

- Hypothesis 4 (H4): A causal relationship exists between human capital efficiency and airlines' return on equity (ROE).

- Hypothesis 5 (H5): A causal relationship exists between customer capital efficiency and airlines' return on equity (ROE).

- Hypothesis 6 (H6): A causal relationship exists between structural capital efficiency and airlines' return on equity (ROE).

The objective of these hypotheses is to ascertain the influence of intellectual capital components on organizational profitability, and to implement the requisite measures and improvements in strategic management. The testing of these hypotheses will contribute to an understanding of the significance of intellectual capital in the aviation sector. The hypotheses will address this gap with a comprehensive and detailed explanation, given the paucity of studies in the existing literature that examine the impact of intellectual capital on financial performance in the aviation sector. Furthermore, the paucity of studies examining the causal relationship has also contributed to the formulation of these hypotheses.

4. Data and Empirical Analysis

4.1. Research Scope

This study examines the influence of intellectual capital on the financial performance of firms, utilizing data from 12 airlines within the Star Alliance for which we have access to common data. The analysis encompasses the period between 2005 and 2023. The airlines included in the study are outlined in Table 1.

Table 1. Airlines included in the analysis

1	Aegan Airlines	7	Lufthansa Airlines
2	Air Canada	8	Scandinavian Airlines
3	Air China	9	Singapore Airlines
4	Air New Zealand	10	Turkish Airlines
5	Copa Airlines	11	Thai Airlines
6	Eva Air	12	United Airlines

4.2. Research Method and Variables

The intellectual capital of the airlines included in the study was initially calculated. The Value-Added Intellectual Coefficient (VAIC) method, developed by Ante Pulic, offers an unconventional perspective for measuring the knowledge possessed by organizations. This method is concerned with the analysis of the performance of intellectual and physical capital, which is necessary for firms to gain a competitive advantage. The VAIC method allows for comparisons to be made at the level of individual firms, as well as between firms and national economies. This is achieved without the need for detailed research, as the data required can be obtained from publicly available sources. Furthermore, the VAIC is employed to assess the efficacy of the values generated by the firm's intangible and tangible assets (Kayalı et al., 2007, p. 71).

The three components used in the calculation of the firm's Value-Added Coefficient are as follows (Sakur and Güngör, 2023, p. 78; Özkan et al., 2017, p. 194):

- Human Capital (Human Capital Efficiency HCE)
- Structural Capital (Structural Capital Efficiency SCE)
- Capital Employed Efficiency (CEE)

1. The value-added calculation according to Ante Public is as follows:

$$VA = OP + EC + D + A$$

VA: represents value added, and is calculated as follows:

OP: represents operating profit,

EC: represents personnel expenses, Depreciation and Amortisation

A: Depreciation Expenses

A review of the literature shows that there are many different approaches to calculating the intellectual capital multiple. The main reason for these differences is that each country has its own unique financial statement content and the data is presented independently. The calculation developed by Public is used by

many researchers in the literature. The simplest and most appropriate formula of value added (Sakur and Güngör, 2023; Ekim et al. 2019; Özkan et al. 2017; Al-musali and Ismail, 2014) is used in the study as in step 1.

2. In order to obtain the intellectual capital multiple (VAIC), it is necessary to calculate the human capital effectiveness (HCE), tangible capital effectiveness (CEE) and structural capital effectiveness (SCE) components of this concept. Public also argued that there is an inverse relationship between human capital and structural capital.

$$HCE = VA/HC$$

$$CEE = VA/CE$$

$$SCE = SC/VA$$

$$SC = VA - HC$$

CE: Book value of the net assets of the affiliated enterprise (Capital Employees)

HC: Personnel costs (human capital)

SC: Structural capital

3. At the end of all these calculations, the values of CEE, HCE, SCE are summed to obtain the value of VAIC in equation 6.

$$VAIC = HCE + SCE + CEE$$

The study uses airline financial performance indicators as the dependent variable. Different ratios are used as financial performance indicators in the literature. The ratios used as financial performance in the analysis are listed below (Firrer and Williams, 2003; Rehman, 2022).

- ROA: Return on assets

- ROE: Return on equity

ROA (Return on Assets) is considered as an important financial indicator that evaluates the efficiency of a company in converting its assets into profit. This ratio determines the level of profit achieved by companies using their total assets and provides valuable information to shareholders, creditors and other stakeholders about the efficiency of management (Elmas & Gözel, 2020, p.223). It also stands out as a key financial performance indicator that is frequently used to measure the profitability performance of companies in their annual reports (Nguyen, 2016, p.29). Looking at the studies that use the return on assets ratio, this ratio is calculated as follows;

$$\text{Return on assets} = \text{Operating profit} / \text{Total assets}$$

Return on equity (ROE) is a financial ratio that measures the return to the company's shareholders on the capital they have invested. A high ROE ratio indicates that the company is using its resources effectively and efficiently. ROE is usually calculated as follows (Rossi and Celenza, 2014).

$$\text{Return on equity} = \text{net profit} / \text{equity}$$

This study analyses the relationship between profitability ratios and intellectual capital of airline companies. First, the unit root test was used to test the stationarity of the data by examining the horizontal cross-sectional dependence of the panel data. The Dumitrescu-Hurlin panel causality analysis was used to test the causality and direction between the dependent and independent variables. Table 2 provides information on the dependent and independent variables included in the analysis. While return on assets and return on equity were employed as dependent variables (Buyuran and Sit, 2021; Sayed and Nefzi, 2024), three principal elements of intellectual capital were utilized as independent variables (Odabaşoğlu, 2018; He and Luo, 2022).

Table 2: Data set and variables

Dependent Variables	Abbreviations	Data source
Roa	ROA	Annual Report
Roe	ROE	Annual Report
Independent Variables		Annual Report
Customer Capital	CE	Annual Report
Human Capital	HE	Annual Report
Structural Capital	SE	Annual Report

Two different econometric models have been developed in the analysis. Their econometric representation is as follows.

$$\text{Model 1: } ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CE_{it} + \beta_2 HE_{it} + \beta_3 SE_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

$$\text{Model 2: } ROE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CE_{it} + \beta_2 HE_{it} + \beta_3 SE_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

i: the number of samples included in the analysis.

t: is the period included in the analysis.

ROA: is the companies' return on assets.

ROE: is the return on equity of the firms.

CE: represents the customer capital ratio of the firms.

HE: is the human capital ratio of the enterprises.

SE: is the structural capital ratio of enterprises

$\varepsilon_{i,t}$: error term

5. Findings

5.1. Cross-Section Dependency Analysis

The intellectual capital and profitability ratios of 12 airlines that are members of the Star Alliance and for which common data are available have been calculated for the years 2005-2023. Before carrying out the econometric analysis to determine the relationship between profitability ratios and intellectual capital, some preliminary tests should be carried out on the airline data that make up the panel. The first of these preliminary tests is the horizontal cross-sectional dependence between the airlines in the panel. Horizontal cross-sectional dependence is defined as a shock that may occur in any of the airline firms that affects the other airline firms (Özşahin, 2016, p. 121). The results of horizontal cross-sectional dependence are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Cross-Section Dependency analysis results

Variable	Test Name	Statistics	d.f.	Prob
ROA	Breusch-Pagan LM	245,142	66.	0,0000
	Pesaran scaled LM	14,547		0,0000
	Bias-corrected scaled LM	14,214		0,0000
	Pesaran CD	11,167		0,0000
ROE	Breusch-Pagan LM	159,641	66.	0,0000
	Pesaran scaled LM	7,105		0,0000
	Bias-corrected scaled LM	6,772		0,0000
	Pesaran CD	7,310		0,0000
CE	Breusch-Pagan LM	186,3527	66.	0,0000
	Pesaran scaled LM	9,430		0,0000
	Bias-corrected scaled LM	9,097		0,0000

	Pesaran CD	9,596		0,0000
HE	Breusch-Pagan LM	228,779	66.	0,0000
	Pesaran scaled LM	13,123		0,0000
	Bias-corrected scaled LM	12,790		0,0000
	Pesaran CD	9,460		0,0000
SE	Breusch-Pagan LM	296,205	66.	0,0000
	Pesaran scaled LM	18,992		0,0000
	Bias-corrected scaled LM	18,659		0,0000
	Pesaran CD	4,065		0,0000

When reviewing the literature, there are several tests to analyse horizontal cross-section dependence. The Berusch-Pagan (1980) CDLM1, Pesaran (2004) CDLM2 and Pesaran (2008) LMadj (bias adjusted) tests were used to test for horizontal cross-section dependence. The main hypotheses for these preliminary tests are H₀: there is no horizontal cross-sectional dependence and H₁: there is horizontal cross-sectional dependence. When analysing the results in Table 3, hypothesis H₀ is rejected and hypothesis H₁ is accepted (p=0.00<0.05). As a result, it can be seen that there is a horizontal cross-sectional dependence among airlines.

5.2. CADF (Cross-sectionally Augmented Dickey-Fuller) Unit Root Test

In this study, when horizontal cross-sectional dependence is found in the analysis, the second-generation panel unit root test is used to test the stationarity of the data. For this reason, the CADF unit root test developed by Pesaran in 2007 was used and formulated as follows (Dursun, 2021, p. 363). The results of the analysis are shown in Table 4.

$$\Delta Y_{i,t} = a_i + b_i Y_{i,t-1} + c_i Y_{t-1} + d_i \Delta Y + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

$\bar{Y}_t$: refers to the cross-sectional average of all alternatives in the panel.

$\Delta \bar{Y}_t$: denotes the first difference of the cross-sectional mean.

$\varepsilon_{i,t}$: error term.

Table 4. CADF Unit root test results

		Stat	Critic Value		
			1%	5%	10%
ROA	constant & trend	-3,061	-3,15	-2,88**	-2,74***
ROE	constant & trend	-3,317	-3,15*	-2,88**	-2,74***
CE	constant & trend	-2,749	-3,15	-2,88	-2,74***
HE	constant & trend	-2,148	-3,15	-2,88	-2,74
DHE	constant & trend	-3,121	-3,15*	-2,88**	-2,74***
SE	constant & trend	-0,828	-3,15	-2,88	-2,74
DSE	constant & trend	-1,653	-3,15	-2,88	-2,74
ROA	constant	-2,38	-2,60	-2,34**	-2,21***
ROE	constant	-2,47	-2,60	-2,34**	-2,21***
CE	constant	-2,48	-2,60	-2,34**	-2,21***
HE	constant	-1,84	-2,60	-2,34	-2,21
DHE	constant	-3,06	-2,60*	-2,34**	-2,21***
SE	constant	-0,276	-2,60	-2,34	-2,21
DSE	constant	-1,48	-2,60	-2,34	-2,21

Note 1: *, **, *** denote significance levels at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

According to the CADF analysis, H₀: there is a unit root. This means that the series is not stationary. H₁: There is no unit root. The series is stationary. According to the CADF unit root test results in Table 4, ROA, ROE and CE are stationary both in level and in trend. The HE value was stationary both in level and in difference. However, SE and its difference are not stationary. Therefore, the analysis was continued by removing the SE value from the model. In other words, the ROA, ROE, CE and DHE values reject hypothesis H₀ and accept hypothesis H₁.

5.3. Dumitrescu-Hurlin Causality Analysis

This is an example of causality analysis developed by Elena-Ivona Dumitrescu and Christophe Hurlin in 2012. The Dumitrescu-Hurlin causality test is designed to test causality and its direction in panel data models. The Dumitrescu-Hurlin test offers three distinct advantages that distinguish it from other panel causality tests. First, the Dumitrescu-Hurlin test gives ideal results when there is horizontal cross-sectional dependence in panel data variables, when there is a mismatch in the time and cross-sectional number of the sample, and when an unbalanced panel is formed. Dumitrescu and Hurlin proposed the following linear model to test panel causality (Aydin, 2019, p. 602).

$$Y_{i,t} = a_i + \sum_{k=1}^K Y_i^{(k)} Y_{i,t-k} + \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_i^{(k)} X_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

β_i : individual fixed effects

$Y_i^{(k)}$: lags

K : lag length

$\beta_i^{(k)}$: slope parameter

$\varepsilon_{i,t}$: error term.

$$H_0 : \beta_i = 0, \forall i = 1, \dots, N$$

$$H_1 : \beta_i = 0, \forall i = 1, \dots, N_1$$

$$\beta_{ii} \neq 0, \forall i = N_1 + 1, N_1 + 2 \dots, N$$

According to Dumitrescu and Hurlin, panel causality, the H0 hypothesis states that there is no causality between the dependent and independent variables, while the H1 hypothesis states that there is causality between the variables. Table 5 shows the results of the Dumitrescu and Hurlin panel causality analysis.

Table 5. Results of Dumitrescu and Hurlin panel causality analysis

Variable	W-Stat.	Zbar-Stat.	Prob.
ROA ≠ MS	2,575	0,206	0,8361
MS → ROA	10,271	9,276	0,0000*
ROA ↔ DIS	5,331	3,263	0,0011*
DIS ↔ ROA	7,184	5,358	0,0000*
ROE ≠ MS	3,581	1,392	0,1637
MS → ROE	14,717	14,516	0,0000*
ROE S ↔ DIS	5,289	3,216	0,0013*
DIS ↔ ROE	5,262	3,185	0,0014*

Note 2: Values with * indicate that there is a causality result (p=0.00<0.05).

Note 3: ≠ means there is no causality, → means there is unidirectional causality, ↔ means there is bidirectional causality.

As a result, according to Dumitrescu and Hurlin's panel causality analysis, the causality analysis with a prob value less than 0.05 rejects the hypothesis H0 and accepts the hypothesis H1. Therefore, it is concluded that there is a positive and unidirectional causality relationship between customer capital and return on assets and equity, and a positive and bidirectional causality relationship between human capital and return on assets and equity. It is also concluded that there is no causality from return on assets and equity to customer capital. As a result of the analyses for the 6 hypotheses developed at the beginning of the study, hypotheses H1, H2, H4 and H5 have been fulfilled.

6. Conclusion

The competitive situation and the conditions that have emerged as a result of the recent changes in business life make it necessary to find new methods and solutions for sustainable activity. In order to keep up with these differentiating conditions, the company must be skilled in producing information, unique in carrying out its activities and strong in its relations with customers and the external environment. In order to have all these characteristics within the company, it must have intellectual capital and be effective in its management and use. Intellectual capital is a key concept for having a say in the marketplace and for sustainable business.

If we look at today's successful companies, we see that they are very successful in incorporating intellectual capital into their development and innovation processes. It is at this point that business leaders should develop strategies to make the most efficient use of tangible and intangible assets.

The efficient use of intellectual capital, one of today's most valuable resources, by incorporating it into the innovation process is possible with the strategic plans put in place beforehand. The efficient use of intellectual capital elements is an essential concept for companies to gain competitive advantage and ensure financial sustainability. In this process, the roles and responsibilities of management are very important. This study analyses the impact of intellectual capital in the airline industry. Twelve airlines that are members of the Star Alliance and for which partner data is available are included in the analysis. First, internal measures of intellectual capital and profitability were calculated and econometric analyses were performed. It is concluded that there is a positive and unidirectional causal relationship between customer capital and return on assets and equity, and a positive and bidirectional causal relationship between human capital and return on assets and equity. It is also concluded that there is no causality from return on assets and equity to customer capital.

It has been observed that hypotheses H1, H2, H4, H5 among the hypotheses developed in the literature have been realised. Hypotheses H1 and H4 posit a positive and bidirectional causal relationship between human capital and return on assets and return on equity. This result is consistent with the findings of Sayed and Nefzi (2024) on Saudi Arabian banks and Erdoğan and Dönmez (2014) in the manufacturing sector. Hypotheses H2 and H5 posit a positive and unidirectional relationship between customer capital and return on assets and return on equity. The findings are corroborated by the research of He and Luo (2022) on the Chinese aviation sector and that of Buyuran and Şit (2021) on the BIST transport sector. In addition, it has been observed in many studies in the literature that human capital, customer capital and structural capital, which are the three elements of intellectual capital, affect the financial performance of companies. For all these reasons, intellectual capital should be given due importance in the sustainability and strategic management of companies. In this way, it will be possible for companies to live a more effective financial life compared to their competitors in the sector in which they operate.

The concept of intellectual capital is very important for the sustainability of airline companies as a service sector. Based on this study, new studies can help to deepen the topic by increasing the sample and the time period. In addition, different economic parameters can be used as a method of analysis.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Ethical approval

Not applicable.

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